

ELIXIR Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens

2026 Hybrid Workshop Report

Amsterdam, Netherlands | 20-21 April 2026

Background

The ELIXIR Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP) workshop was organised as part of a co-located Science Tier meeting and brought together contributors working across the biodiversity, food security, and pathogens areas of ELIXIR. The workshop materials framed the meeting around a collaborative mindset, interaction, sharing of knowledge and opportunities, and the goal of finalising the first draft of the 2027-2028 BFSP work programme.

Event Format and Participation

The workshop took place in hybrid format on 20-21 April 2026 at the Park Inn by Radisson Amsterdam City West in Amsterdam, the Netherlands, with remote participation via Zoom. The agenda combined short project updates, a roundtable discussion, structured work on the 2027-2028 work programme, Work Package (WP) breakouts, a strategy discussion, and a session on funding and collaborations.

There were 35 onsite attendees on both days each, alongside 22 online attendees on day one and 19 online attendees on day two (total 57 attendees on day one; 54 attendees on day two). Participants included representatives from ELIXIR Nodes, the ELIXIR Hub, BFSP co-leads, WP leads, WP task leads, and contributors to the 2027-2028 BFSP work programme.

Event Content

Day one started with short updates from the nine funded [BFSP 2024-2026 Open Call projects](#). These updates covered plant pan-genome standards, quality control, and visualisation in [E-PAN](#); FAIR Galaxy workflows, benchmarking, training materials, and machine-learning based resource prediction in [FAIRyMAGs](#); FAIRification of plant datasets and updates to the RDMkit in [HARVEST](#); the [Odyssey](#) application for connecting molecular and geographical biodiversity data; domain-aware FAIR evaluation in [BioDiv-FAIR-Checker](#); metadata template development for [non-human pathogen data](#); the [MetaBuddy](#) virtual assistant for collecting metadata for plant datasets; [FAIRferm](#) activities around time-series food fermentation data, FAIR submission, SOPs, and workflows; and [KYBELE](#)'s AI-assisted pipeline for extracting biodiversity

knowledge from literature. The roundtable discussion highlighted several cross-cutting themes. Participants discussed how BFSP activities can learn from each other across domains, the need for shared vocabularies and standards, the role of knowledge graphs and LLM-based methods for extracting information from publications and supplementary material, the importance of training outputs and tool visibility, and possible routes to stronger engagement with industry, especially in areas such as fermentation and agrifood data practices.

The remainder of day one was dedicated to the 2027-2028 work programme. The co-leads reported that 32 expressions of interest had been received and clustered into the most represented tasks, after which expressions of interest for leadership and participation were opened to build core groups. The work plan structure presented at the workshop consisted of one management work package (WP1) and four thematic WPs: WP2 Federation, WP3 FAIR Data, WP4 Analysis, and WP5 Standards. Breakout sessions were then held for the thematic WPs, with online breakout rooms and shared working files. Reporting back from the breakouts showed convergence around several priorities.

WP2 Federation discussions focused on brokering tools such as MADBOT and ISA Wizard and on progressing Community Resource Catalogues. WP3 FAIR Data discussions focused on aligning phenotyping and environmental data models, standardising biodiversity and environmental genomics data across the full data life cycle, and converging literature-mining use cases around biotic interactions. WP4 Analysis discussions focused on FAIRification of analytical workflows, possible translation between Galaxy and Nextflow workflows, and AI- and knowledge-graph based use cases around pathogen-host interactions. WP5 Standards discussions focused on ontology and data-model gap analysis, extending standards such as EDAM and PHIPO, and developing AI/ML benchmarking frameworks aligned with outputs from the Analysis WP.

Day two began with a recap of the work programme drafting and a reminder of the information still needed in the CoS working document, including objectives, task descriptions, deliverables and milestones, expected outcomes and impacts, partnerships and person-month effort, community engagement, and training outputs. Final WP reporting reaffirmed the directions agreed on day one. The second day also included a consultation on shaping the next version of the current [BFSP strategy](#), and a session on funding and collaborations which was presented by the Hub's Head of External Relations. These discussions covered Horizon Europe opportunities for 2026 and 2027, follow-up opportunities linked to AgroServ, relations with other ESFRI and ERIC infrastructures, ongoing discussion with GBIF, the priority given to DISSCO, and the question of how BFSP should engage with future European programmes and possible industry partners.

Outcomes and Conclusion

The workshop made substantial progress towards its main goal of producing the first draft of the BFSP 2027-2028 work programme. By the end of the meeting, the thematic WPs had refined task scopes, leads, expected outputs, and cross-WP links sufficiently for consolidation into a single draft document for review by ELIXIR Heads of Nodes.

The next steps presented at the workshop were to merge the WP sections written into one document, circulate that version for review and comments – including an opportunity for the addition of more in-kind participants where relevant, work on the budget using actual person-month rates, fine-tune contributions and cross-WP alignment, and aim for a final work plan by June 2026. The strategy discussion also identified broader points for follow-up, including whether the current BFSP strategy should be reviewed by other research infrastructures, how widely it should be disseminated, what lessons from the expression-of-interest process should be carried forward, and how future planning should better support earlier coordination and communication. Overall, the workshop demonstrated strong engagement across the BFSP area. The combination of funded-project reporting, roundtable discussion, structured breakout work, strategy consultation, and funding discussion helped move BFSP from a set of ongoing project activities towards a more coordinated programme for 2027-2028.

Acknowledgements

We thank the ELIXIR Hub, BFSP co-leads, WP leads, task leads, speakers, and all participants for their active contributions, both on-site and online. Their engagement and collaborative approach were essential in shaping the next work programme (2027-2028) for the ELIXIR BFSP Science Tier.